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An Approach to Increasing the Reuse of Scientific Software

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The Reuse of Software is Central to Research Efficiency & Scientific Exchange

Why is it important?

- It enables the reproduction and validation of results
- It enables the understanding and comparison of methods and approaches
- It reduces redundant software developments that must be individually documented, maintained and further developed
- It increases software quality, since larger developer and user communities translate into more expertise and larger work forces

What are current problems?

- Relevant software is hard to find
- Software is published without license, metadata and or insufficient documentation
 - Documentation standards often do not exist or are not adhered to
 - Documentation is only rarely available in a machine-actionable form
- The provision of this information is often associated with a high level of effort

Facilitating Four Areas of the Software Life Cycle

Facilitating Software Description

What metadata do we need?

- **Detailed interface description** in addition to **general software metadata** such as author, license and date created
- Metadata must be semantically enriched to be **machine-actionable** (that is, using ontology terms instead of free text)

Building on existing standards

- CodeMeta¹ for general software metadata
- OpenAPI² as interface description standard

The documentation effort must be low!

- **Tool support** for creating metadata
- Metadata annotations are partially **embedded in the source code** supporting code documentation which must be done anyway

¹<https://codemeta.github.io/> ²<https://www.openapis.org/>

Facilitating Software Publishing

Describing software with metadata only once enables many applications.

- Once software is described with metadata, a metadata exchange file is generated
- Upload to many different software publication platforms:
 - a. Documentation publication platforms (e.g., ReadTheDocs¹)
 - b. Software repository platforms for sharing source code (e.g., GitHub²)
 - c. Software publication platforms for package management (e.g., PyPi³)
 - d. Software registry platforms for finding software (e.g., Open Energy Platform⁴)
- Both, using standards and fostering machine-actionability increase the likelihood of widespread dissemination

¹<https://readthedocs.org/>

²<https://github.com/>

³<https://pypi.org/>

⁴<https://openenergy-platform.org/>

```

73 @xattr(xattr={
74   "HubHeight" : [ ("unit_type", "distance"), ("unit", "meters")],
75   "PowerMeasurement" : (
76     "dimensions",
77     {
78       "location_of_measurement" : {
79         "unit_type": "location",
80         "unit": "country name"
81       },
82       "time_of_measurement" : {
83         "unit_type": "time",
84         "unit": "days since 1895-01-01"
85       }
86     }
87   ),
88   "subtract_value" : [
89     ("is_interface_function", True),
90     {
91       "minuend" : [
92         ("domain", "real"),
93         ("input_output", "input")
94       ],
95       "subtrahend" : [
96         ("domain", "real"),
97         ("input_output", "input")
98       ],
99     }
100   ]
101 })
102 class PowerOutputCalculator:
103     """This is a simple calculator class"""
104     HubHeight: int
105     PowerMeasurement: pd.DataFrame
106
107     def subtract_value(self, minuend : int, subtrahend : int):
108         difference = minuend - subtrahend
109         return difference
    
```

Interface annotation
in source code


```

Swagger Editor
1 openapi: 3.0.0
2 info:
3   title: My Spec
4   version: 1.0.0
5   paths: {}
6   components:
7     schemas:
8     PowerOutputCalculator:
9       type: object
10      description: This is a simple calculator class
11      properties:
12        HubHeight:
13          type: integer
14          x-unit_type: distance
15          x-unit: meters
16        PowerMeasurement:
17          type: object
18          x-dimensions:
19            location_of_measurement:
20              unit_type: location
21              unit: country name
22            time_of_measurement:
23              unit_type: time
24              unit: days since 1895-01-01
25      x-functions:
26        subtract_value:
27          type: object
28          x-is_interface_function: true
29      properties:
30        minuend:
31          type: integer
32          x-domain: real
33          x-input_output: input
34        subtrahend:
35          type: integer
36          x-domain: real
37          x-input_output: input
38      required:
39        - minuend
40        - subtrahend
41      required:
42        - HubHeight
43        - PowerMeasurement
    
```

Resulting metadata
exchange file

My Spec 1.0.0 OAS3

No operations defined in spec!

Schemas

PowerOutputCalculator {

- description: This is a simple calculator class
- HubHeight* integer
x-unit_type: distance
x-unit: meters
- PowerMeasurement* {
 - x-dimensions {
 - location_of_measurement: {
 - unit_type: location
 - unit: country name
 - time_of_measurement: {
 - unit_type: time
 - unit: days since 1895-01-01

- x-functions {
- subtract_value: {
 - type: object
 - x-is_interface_function: true
 - properties: {
 - minuend: {
 - type: integer
 - x-domain: real
 - x-input_output: input
 - subtrahend: {
 - type: integer
 - x-domain: real
 - x-input_output: input
 - required: [minuend, subtrahend]

Generated
documentation website¹

¹Utilization of the Swagger Editor: <https://editor.swagger.io/>

Facilitating Software Search

- Detailed and machine-actionable software metadata improve software search
 - Different research artifacts are linked together via their metadata¹
 - Implementation of semantic search methods that can be used across artifacts (e.g., search for existing data or software which produces the requested data)
- Crawling and generating software metadata from publication platforms for software not adhering to this approach

¹E.g. in the Open Research Knowledge Graph: <https://orkg.org/>

Facilitating Software Reuse

- Focus on innovative downstream applications
 - Automated data validation against software interfaces
 - Automated data conversion for matching software interfaces
 - Automated compilation of software and data to software workflows
- Development of interface design guidelines

Thank you!

Comments and
questions are
welcome.

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